

STRESS AND FAILURE ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE BICYCLE FRAMES

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ABSTRACT

An analytical and experimental investigation was conducted to study three carbon fiber Olympic class track bicycle frames designed at McGill University. A finite element software was used for geometry development, laminate configuration, and for predicting failure using the maximum stress criteria. A load case simulating actual riding conditions was used. The stresses in each of the composite layers are found to be lower than the allowable stresses because of a properly designed geometry and laminate. Combining the experimental and theoretical results, a good understanding of the critical problems related to composite bicycle frame design was obtained.

INTRODUCTION

The use of advanced composite materials is becoming increasingly common. From airplane wings to canoe hulls, composites are now everywhere. The sporting goods industry has also turned to advanced composite materials for performance improvements. The use of composite materials in such sports as cycling, sailing, and tennis, for example, is now very common. The cycling industry in particular adopted advanced composites more than 10 years ago in the construction of frames. The use of advanced composite materials in this industry has created changes in the materials, geometry and construction techniques of bicycle frames. Advanced composites are being used because of savings in weight as well as improvements in stiffness and aerodynamics. The use of composite materials in complex structures where applied loads are not well known as in a bicycle frame in motion is a difficult design challenge. Hence a thorough loading, stress and failure analysis of composite bicycle frames is critically important. This allows the determination of highly stressed areas so that reinforcement can be implemented to prevent failure under normal riding conditions.

One of the first attempts in the design and commercialization of a composite material bicycle came in 1982 from Sweden with the Itera plastic bicycle [1]. Although the injection molded bicycle had high projected sales, the project failed completely because people were not ready for a change in bicycle shape and riding feel. The Itera bicycle did not feel like a steel frame and the styling of this new bicycle was never accepted. This example is a reminder that the cycling community is one which has traditionally been very conservative and reluctant to change from the traditional diamond shape structure. Since the traditional diamond shape structure was so deeply entrenched in designers' and manufacturers' minds, the only way to introduce the new advanced composite materials into the cycling industry was to use composites tubes to replace the steel and aluminum ones. The joining of the composite tubes was done using metallic lugs. However, the use of composites in this way is less than optimum and can create problems, depending on the joining material used, such as galvanic corrosion at the tube-lug interface, different thermal expansion coefficients of the dissimilar materials, and uneven distribution of stresses creating poor load paths at the tube intersections [2]. Although some of these problems have been alleviated in recent years with the use of composite and titanium lugs and inserts, a composite bicycle frame should evolve in a structure where loads are carried by a low mass monocoque skin of large surface area rather than a tube-lug design [3]. Several high performance bicycle frames have been constructed this

way including Chris Boardman's LOTUS frame which he used to win the 1992 gold medal at the Barcelona Olympics in the 4000m pursuit [4]. But no complete study on stress and failure analysis of high performance composite monocoque bicycle frames is reported and well documented in the literature.

Stress analysis using finite element techniques is a good way to analyze a complex composite structure. Many published studies document the use of finite element analysis in the design of traditional frames [5-8]. The simplest way to do a finite element analysis on the traditional diamond structure is to use beam elements to model the tubes. This method can accurately model the tube parameters of thickness, outside diameter and material properties. If sufficient number of elements are utilized, double butting of tubes can also be easily incorporated. Fig. 1 shows the diamond frame bicycle terminology.

Figure 1. Diamond frame bicycle terminology

Using this method and a load case where a cyclist is in a sprint out of the pedals, it was found that the maximum stress was at the intersection of the down tube and the seat tube at the bottom bracket [9]. A study of the same type, but considering rider induced loads at different crank angles combined with handlebar and seat loads, found that the maximum stress is at the top and seat tube intersection [5]. The beam model approach is approximate as it does not consider the actual tube joining regions where large stresses and failure usually occurs. This is why the use of shell elements to model the tubes themselves and the joints has also been considered [6]. Shell models allow the determination of the different tube stresses around the circumference, something that beam models cannot provide. But it was shown that deflection measurements on both shell and beam finite element models were very similar for static loading cases [8]. Combined with the fact that the strengths of the different tubes have to be high enough to prevent failure, it is desirable that the frame be stiff in certain regions and compliant in others. It is desirable to have a stiff head tube and bottom bracket region in order to prevent extreme deformations in cases of high loading during intense riding. On the other hand a vertically compliant frame would be desirable for riding comfort. Hence characterization of bicycle frames has to be done in terms of strength in order to assure structural integrity but also has to be done in terms of stiffness in order to produce a good frame. Frames can also be characterized by the strain energy absorbed into the frame during pedaling. As energy is most effectively transferred through a stiff structure from the rider's body to the back wheel, a minimum of strain energy absorbed in the frame under loading is desirable [7].

It is difficult to compare bicycle frames since each researcher and manufacturer utilizes a different loading case or test method to characterize frames. This is so because there are very few standards for the determination of performance of bicycle frames. The existing standards are for security and structural integrity and cannot be used directly to compare performance and rigidity of different frames. These standards offer only static and dynamic testing where one load is applied to one point whereas this is not what happens in actual riding situations. Hence the standards are only useful to make sure that bicycles respect a certain baseline of structural integrity but not as a design tool for high performance racing bicycles.

Since it is believed that high performance track and time trial composite bicycles should evolve into the shape of monocoque tubeless frames, the lessons learned from the finite element analysis of tubular frames may not be relevant. This research is thus aimed at using finite element methods to perform stress analysis on monocoque composite frames rather than on conventional tubular frames. Another study on monocoque composite material frames has been done but concentrates on the construction process and testing, however no finite element analysis was performed [3].

Also a study of a composite mountain bike was done but only considers finite element static loading in one location to be compared with the actual prototype, and does not review the stresses in riding conditions [10]. The use of a geometrically efficient structure combined with the desirable properties of composites, a correct understanding of the loading conditions, as well as stress and failure analysis allows for the development of a good composite bicycle frame. This paper thus presents results of ongoing research at McGill University on monocoque composite frame design.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

The finite element analysis of the monocoque bicycle frames was performed using SDRC's I-DEAS finite element software[11]. This software is particularly appropriate for this type of structure as it incorporates both a very good laminate modeling section with good 3-D solid modeling.

GEOMETRY

The geometry of the frame is the first parameter to fix in a study of this type. The first step in geometry development was to invent as many possible geometries based on observation and engineering intuition. From the initial geometries, three were kept after initial stress and deflection analysis was done. The three frame geometries studied are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Frame Geometry

The shape of prototype 1 was chosen because it possesses a similar geometry to the LOTUS. Prototype 2 models a beam which extends from the rear dropouts to the top of the head tube. Prototype 3 is actually a modification of the ZIPP bike which is on the market now. The modification is that prototype 3 contains a seat beam; a feature which is not part of the original design. This modification allows a reduction of the lateral sway and vertical movement associated with the cantilevered seat design of the ZIPP. A stress and failure analysis was performed on these three models. The three frames were modeled using thin shell triangular and quadrilateral elements. The FEA models do not contain an internal core that constructed prototypes would have. The introduction of the internal core was done as an aid to fabrication and has only a small influence on the stress state. Prototype 1, 2 and 3 contain respectively 2260, 1558, and 2156 elements.

MATERIAL AND LAMINATE CONFIGURATION

The material used for the modeling and construction of the frames is unidirectional and woven high strength carbon/epoxy prepreg. The fibers are AKZO HTA7. The woven material is a CFS001 4X4 weave which conforms quite well to double curvatures. The epoxy system (LTM 25) is low temperature curing in order to be compatible with the construction method. Laminates for different elements of the 3 prototypes were modeled using the laminate modeling capability of the software. The 0 degree direction for the laminate construction is taken to be the direction of a vector going from the rear dropouts to the top of the head tube. The laminates discussed below are the result of an evolutive study in which many types of laminates were attempted in order to develop a close to optimum fiber orientation for each case in terms of strength, stiffness and ease of fabrication.

Prototype 1 includes 5 different laminates containing woven and unidirectional material and corresponding to different layouts used at different locations. It should be noted that this particular prototype was modeled and constructed only as a verification of the finite element analysis result and construction method. Hence this particular frame could not be used in a riding or racing situation as it was not designed nor conceived to do so. Unidirectional material was used in conjunction with the woven material in certain high load areas as reinforcement. The regions of high loads were matched with the regions of material overlap since those regions have more material to support the load. The overlap regions were at least 25mm which well exceeds the load transfer length required. Hence overlaps actually worked as reinforcement.

Two laminates were considered for prototype 2. The first laminate used only unidirectional material applied on the model. It contained a $[0_2/90]_6$ layer laminate in the low load regions built up with overlaps to a 10 layer $[0_2/90_2/0]_6$ laminate in higher load areas. This laminate was not adopted for construction as after the construction of prototype 1 it was realized that the use of unidirectional material on a structure as complex as a bicycle frame was very problematic. It was thus attempted to model prototype 2 with woven material only, because even if the unidirectional reinforcement provides better stiffness and strength, it is believed that the construction process would be accelerated with the use of woven fabric. Hence another laminate using woven material was developed. The laminate modeled for this prototype was made of 3 layers of woven material in low stress areas and a buildup to 6 layers in the overlap regions. This prototype was also modeled using 45° woven reinforcement in the bottom bracket area as will be discussed later.

The laminate for prototype 3 was modeled using unidirectional material only. A $[0_2/90]_6$ laminate with overlap reinforcement in critical regions is modeled. This frame is still in the laminate development stages.

LOADING AND BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

The loading and boundary conditions for a study of this type are very important in order to obtain realistic results. A bicycle frame in motion is a complex loaded structure. In order to perform a reasonable stress analysis it is thus important to choose a load case which closely represents the riding conditions. Track racing is performed under controlled road conditions and thus only rider induced loads were considered here. Although this assumption is quite valid for track racing, it certainly is not for mountain biking. A load case where only one load is applied at a specific location, the pedals for example, with stress and displacement patterns obtained throughout the frame is too simplistic. An analysis of this type would only inform the designer about the specific response to a certain load and not the response of the frame to a riding situation. The load case chosen for this study contains loads applied to the frame by a racer riding on a flat surface at 50km/hr developing an average power of 396W [12]. This load case was calculated analytically and corresponds closely to what has been measured for the maximum loads in another study where loads at different application points were measured as a function of crank angle [13]. This particular load case is different from others used in other studies as it considers the non-negligible effect of the chain and thus renders the loading situation non-symmetric. Hence it is not possible to use symmetry to reduce the number of elements on the frame.

Rigid beam elements were used to model the handlebars, pedals, and front fork allowing the loads to be applied at correct points and transferred to the shell elements. In the regions of the seat and rear dropout, the load is divided up and applied to many nodes directly on the shell model. The restraint set chosen attempted to model the restraint on a riding bicycle frame as closely as possible. This restraint set has been previously used in other bicycle frame stress studies [13]. The frame was restrained at the bottom of the front fork as well as the left and right rear dropout. The restraints are summarized in Table 1. The coordinate system used is shown in Fig. 1.

Table 1. Riding Restraints

	X	Y	Z	X rot.	Y rot.	Z rot.
Bottom of front fork		*	*	*	*	
Left rear dropout		*	*		*	
Right rear dropout	*	*	*		*	

In the above table, * denotes a fixed degree of freedom.

STRESS ANALYSIS RESULTS

The stress analysis was performed using the above loads and boundary conditions. A plane stress state was assumed, and stresses were found in each of the laminate layers. Normal stresses in the x- and y-directions as well as the in-plane shear stress was obtained.

The maximum stresses for prototype 1 were obtained for each layer of each laminate. The stresses are tabulated in failure index form (stress divided by strength). The failure index for this prototype was calculated with the failure stress of the material at the location of the maximum stress for each layer. The X direction refers to the material orientation direction in the plane of the elements that was defined from the rear dropouts to the head tube. The Y direction is a direction perpendicular to the X direction in the plane of the element. Table 2 shows the failure indices for each material failure mode in each ply.

Table 2. Prototype 1: Maximum failure index for each layer

	Xtension	Xcomp.	Ytension	Ycomp.	XYshear
Ply 1	0.092	0.196	0.049	0.080	0.493
Ply 2	0.043	0.168	0.085	0.168	0.628
Ply 3	0.042	0.193	0.082	0.144	0.633
Ply 4	0.031	0.067	0.083	0.083	0.494
Ply 5*	0.047	0.225	0.004	0.008	0.280

*Unidirectional layer

Table 3 shows the failure indices for the second prototype, again subjected to the same loading and restraint set as prototype 1.

Table 3. Prototype 2: Maximum failure index for each layer

	X tension	Xcomp.	Ytension	Ycomp.	XYshear
Ply 1	0.138	0.172	0.075	0.170	0.744
Ply 2	0.124	0.156	0.077	0.170	0.763
Ply 3	0.126	0.169	0.099	0.142	0.782
Ply 4	0.043	0.175	0.040	0.114	0.660
Ply 5	0.033	0.122	0.036	0.186	0.679
Ply 6	0.049	0.185	0.067	0.140	0.692

For prototype 3 results of a ply-by-ply analysis were obtained as for prototype 1 and 2, but only the maximum failure indices and the plies in which they occur are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Prototype 3: Maximum failure index for all layers

	X tension	Xcomp.	Ytension	Ycomp.	XY shear
Max.F.I.	0.160	0.060	0.770	0.224	0.187
Ply #	3	5&6	8	8	2

DISCUSSION

It is interesting to note trends from the above results. The largest failure indices for the first prototype are due to in-plane shear stresses. Fig. 3 shows the XY shear stress contours in the first woven ply. The largest shear stress region occurs near the edge of the front curvature of the frame. From this analysis, it can be seen that more 45° layers would be needed in the front and back curvature regions. This observation corresponds to the practice for tubular carbon fiber frames where the down tube is made mostly with 45° layers in order to resist down tube torsion. Hence for this first prototype, with this particular laminate an in-plane shear failure is expected.

Figure 3. Shear stress contours for prototype 1

For prototype 2, the highest stresses were again due to shear but in the region of the bottom bracket especially on the left side of the bicycle where the chain is located. Fig. 4 shows the shear stresses in the bottom bracket region. The shear stress varies from a positive value to a negative value within a small region. Considering the large stress values in that location as seen in Table 3, reinforcement was added to this region. Two 45° woven layers were added to the 6 layer laminate already present in this region. This allowed not only the shear stresses to be reduced but also the X and Y normal stresses reduced as well. The shear stress in particular reduced by up to 35% in one of the plies. One aspect however is that the location of the maximum stress did not change. Hence a geometric redesign would be necessary in this area. A bottom bracket geometry like prototype 1 is much more sturdy and hence the stresses there are better distributed.

Figure 4 Prototype 2 - Shear stresses at the bottom bracket

The addition of the two 45° layers also increased the overall stiffness tremendously as seen by reductions in frame deflections. Table 5 shows the displacement at the bottom bracket before and after the addition of the 45° reinforcement. The large X displacement is due to the large chain force, and the reinforcement greatly improves the stiffness in this direction. In the Y direction the displacement is not particularly affected by the laminate change as the vertical displacement is mostly due to the overall flexing of the frame rather than a local effect. The bottom bracket torsion stiffness is much improved with the addition of the reinforcement as can be seen with the reduction of the Z direction displacement. Fig. 5 shows the scalar magnitude of the displacements throughout the frame. It is to be noted that the contours are not symmetric about the xy-plane.

As previously discussed, the strain energy absorbed by the frame is another good indication of the stiffness and hence performance of a frame. With the addition of the 45° reinforcements in an area representing only 18% of the total frame shell areas, the total strain energy absorbed by the frame

was reduced by 30%. Hence adding only local reinforcement with minimal weight penalty to the structure results in a large improvement in overall stiffness, and thus performance.

Table 5. Bottom bracket displacement with and without reinforcement

	Without reinforcement (mm)	With reinforcement (mm)
X_{global}	2.9	1.8
Y_{global}	-2.2	-2.0
Z_{global}	3.0	2.2

Figure 5. Displacement contours for prototype 2

For prototype 3, the study is still in evolution but preliminary results have shown that the largest stress concentrations occur at the intersection of the down tube with the main beam. The shape and the reinforcement of this joint will be crucial for the success of a frame of this type. For this prototype however, it is noted that the largest failure index is in the matrix tension mode. This arises because the material used is unidirectional reinforcement that is much more subject to matrix failure than woven material.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

The experimental part of the research consists of the fabrication of the prototypes and the testing of the fabricated frame. The construction of the frames is done on an individual basis. As the research is still in the prototyping stage, mass production methods such as the use of expensive and sophisticated molds are not used. The frames were constructed by wrapping carbon fiber prepreg over an internal PVC foam core. Aluminum inserts were used at the rear dropouts, head tube, and bottom bracket in order to meet with the other bicycle components. The frame was then vacuum bagged and cured at the appropriate temperature for the prescribed time (60°C for 12.5 hr. for this epoxy system). The foam used for the first prototype has a density of 75 kg/m³ while the second prototype will be constructed with an internal core of 45 kg/m³. The first reason for using a lower density foam in the second prototype was weight reduction. The first prototype has a foam weight of 901g for a total frame weight of 2183g which is quite substantial. The aluminum inserts weighed 603g while the carbon/epoxy prepreg accounted for 679g. With the use of the lower density foam, and a design improvement of the inserts, a substantial weight reduction would be possible. The weight for prototype 2 should be in the 1.5 kg range (450g foam, 250g aluminum inserts, 800g carbon/epoxy) which is very competitive compared to other monocoque bicycles frames. Hence a reduction of the foam density reduces the overall frame weight substantially. The second reason for lower density foam material is an improvement in the dynamic behaviour of the frame. It was shown that a lower density internal core improves the dynamic properties by increasing the natural frequencies of the frame [10]. The third reason for reducing the foam weight

The second part of the experimental investigation was the testing and comparison of the constructed frame. Experimental testing can be done in order to validate the finite element results, or to compare the tested frame with previously tested frames. In this case a simple comparison with the finite element model was performed. Prototype 1 was tested in a specially built static testing jig which can apply one load at a certain location and allow the displacement to be measured at another location. Two single-load static tests were considered. The results of these experimental and finite element comparisons are shown in Table 7. The test methods are the same as the ones documented in another study by the authors[12].

Table 7. Comparison between finite element and experimental results for prototype 1

Prototype 1	Out-of-plane deflection (mm)	In-plane deflection (mm)
FEA	14.76	2.70
Actual prototype	14.5	2.5

The results show that the finite element model exhibits overall deflections similar to the constructed prototype, and hence a certain confidence in the results is obtained.

CONCLUSION

Many factors enter into the design of a composite monocoque track bicycle, including geometry, weight, riding loads, and desired performance characteristics. The use of finite element analysis to address these factors can be quite successful, but requires a good understanding of appropriate boundary conditions, load cases, material behavior, and failure criteria. We have shown that the analysis can be effective for determining both geometry and laminate design to obtain better strength and stiffness characteristics. The addition of local reinforcement has been shown to reduce local stresses as well as to greatly reduce the amount of strain energy stored in the bicycle frame, thus increasing the power delivered to the pedals. Local reinforcement can be added to the frame with a minimum increase in overall weight and should be used to the extent possible.

This study has presented a methodology for the design of a monocoque carbon fiber frame using finite element analysis, and is part of ongoing research into the development and construction of high performance track bicycles.

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